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Malaria and economic growth: revisiting the evidence

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Malaria and Economic Growth: Revisiting the Evidence

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1 Introduction

The global incidence rate of malaria decreased by 18% between 2010 and 2016. Despite this decline, there were 216 million cases worldwide with 80% of the global disease burden borne by 15 Sub-Saharan countries and India alone [1]. The association between illness and poverty has been much addressed in the academic literature and malaria, particularly, has received a substantial share of this attention. Due to its intractable nature and geographic concentration, malaria is still considered a serious challenge to economic development.

A highly cited paper by Gallup and Sachs [2] (henceforth, GS) quantified the adverse effect of malaria on economic outcomes looking at differences across countries at specific points in time between 1965 and 1995. The authors found that malarial countries displayed, *ceteris paribus*, per capita income levels and annual per capita growth rates that were, respectively, 70 and 1.3 percent lower than non-malarial countries. Whether in levels or in terms of growth rates, these were large numbers and they still shape the global agenda with regard to the disease. Since publication of their celebrated paper, many wide-reaching interventions have been undertaken. Coverage of insecticide-treated mosquito nets (ITN) and indoor residual spraying (IRS) has increased in the past decade but also levelled off in recent years [1].

Similarly, malarial incidence, i.e. cases per thousand inhabitants at risk, despite being lower than in 2010, has witnessed a lower rate of decline. The findings by GS suggest that the payoffs to malaria control or eradication could indeed be substantial. The purpose of this paper is to ascertain whether the claims of GS can be substantiated in light of (i) the vastly improved and more recent data on malaria prevalence and other determinants of economic growth that are now available and (ii) the much higher econometric standards

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in terms of identification strategies that are now the professional norm. It is worth noting that a “pure” replication of the GS paper using updated data is not possible because a number of explanatory variables are no longer maintained or have been superseded by alternative measures or techniques. We also propose an original identification strategy to establish the causal link between malaria and GDP per capita using measures of drug resistance.

We find that malaria eradication: (i) would be associated with a 5% increase in per capita GDP on average; (ii) would be associated with a 1% increase in the annual growth rate of GDP per capita; (iii) would disproportionately benefit the world’s poorest countries. While our numbers are substantial, they are significantly smaller than those reported in the original work by GS. This is probably inevitable in that the marginal benefits to eradication have been reduced by concerted international action over the past fifteen years. These efforts have already led to a substantial dividend being reaped by the world’s poorest countries, as a consequence of reductions in malaria incidence.

2 Methods

We provide below a brief summary of the empirical methods used in GS and describe the points of departure in our estimations.

2.1 The original empirical specifications

The original GS paper uses econometric specifications that are cross-country in nature and do not include a time dimension. The GDP per capita regressions in GS are based on the following specification:

$$y_i = x_i\alpha + m_i\beta + u_i, \tag{1}$$

where i indexes countries, y_i represents log GDP per capita in 1995 (except for one regression, in which the year is 1955), and x_i is a matrix of covariates that includes: the percentage of the population within 100km of the coast, the log of the minimum distance to major world markets (New York, Rotterdam and Tokyo), log hydrocarbon reserves per person, and the percentage of a country’s land area which is located in the geographical tropics. Depending upon the specification, other covariates include whether the country was socialist, was a former colony, an index of trade openness (the so-called Sachs-Warner measure) and an index of the quality of public institutions. Their key explanatory variable m_i , the *falciparum* malaria index, is given by the product of the fraction of the population living in areas with high malaria risk in 1965 times the fraction of malaria cases in 1990 that are due to *P. falciparum*. Finally, u_i represents the error term that includes country-specific unobservable factors that are not captured in the data.

Equation (1) yields the shortfall in GDP per capita due to malaria by comparing malarial to non-malarial countries (see Table 1, p. 87 in their paper). The point estimate of the coefficient β associated with m_i implies that, *ceteris paribus*, the ratio of per capita GDP for malarial ($m_i=1$) versus non-malarial ($m_i=0$) countries is: $\frac{y_i|_{m_i=1}}{y_i|_{m_i=0}} = 0.29$. Adding other covariates to their baseline specification changes this basic result very little.

The specification used by GS to investigate the relationship between malaria and GDP per capita *growth* is given by:

$$\Delta y_i = x_i\alpha + m_i\beta + \Delta m_i\gamma + u_i, \quad (2)$$

where, once again, i indexes countries, Δy_i is the annual growth rate of GDP per capita between 1965 and 1990, and x_i is a matrix of covariates usually measured in the *initial* period: in this case, log initial GDP per capita and measures of initial human capital including log secondary schooling enrolment rate, log life expectancy at birth and those mentioned earlier. As in equation (1), the key explanatory variable is m_i : the initial (i.e. 1965) *falciparum* malaria index; with the addition of Δm_i : the *change* in the *falciparum* index between 1965 and 1994. The error term u_i , as before, represents country-specific unobservable factors. The cost of 1.3% lost annual growth due to malaria is provided by the coefficient β associated with m_i in column 5 of their Table 7 (p. 92). Their results are based on estimating equation (2) with or without including Δm_i by Ordinary Least Squares (OLS).¹

2.2 Updated data

In order to identify the relationship between the incidence of malaria and economic outcomes and establish what might be a plausibly causal link, we use data from 180 countries over the 2000-15 period. Panel data, which include a time dimension, allow us to look at changes *within* countries and not just *across* them. By controlling for country-specific characteristics that do not change over time, all remaining variation in the dependent variable is due to factors that vary over time, such as malarial intensity. We attempt to keep with the spirit of the original GS specifications wherever the latter is not feasible. To a large extent, covariates referring to a country’s geographical characteristics such as distance to major markets, percent of tropical land area or population share within 100 km from the coast are accounted for by the country-specific fixed effects in a panel data specification since they are time invariant (more on this below). The same applies to historical characteristics such as whether the country was a former colony or socialist.

The cross-country regressions in this paper include indicators from the GeoDist dataset of CEPII for whether the country is landlocked or a former colony. The quality of institutions is captured by the rule of law estimate from the World Governance Indicators and trade openness by trade as a percent of GDP from the World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI). The covariates relating to human capital such as life expectancy at birth and net enrolment in secondary schooling are also from WDI. The improved measure

¹There is one exception to this: an instrumental variables (IV) specification in which Δm_i is instrumented using the prevalence of 53 different *anopheles* mosquito vectors in each country in 1952 as exclusion restrictions. Note that, by current standards, it is likely that this IV strategy suffers from a severe weak instruments problem since many if not all of the exclusion restrictions are likely to be statistically insignificant. Moreover, while under the null hypothesis of valid instruments the IV estimator is consistent, it does suffer from finite sample bias, with that bias growing with the number of instruments and with their weakness [3]. While GS note that the first-stage reduced form has an R-squared of 0.51, it is not presented in the paper, and as such we do not know whether this corresponds to the *partial* R-squared once the impact of the other covariates (x_i) has been accounted for. That the exogeneity of the malaria index is not rejected by the appropriate Hausman test, as they report, may simply stem from the weakness of the identification provided by the proposed IVs.

of education given by the Barro-Lee average years of schooling in the population aged 15 years and above is available only for 5 year periods. This is included in estimations which use 5 year averages instead of yearly data.

The dependent variables are the level of Gross Domestic Product per capita (at Purchasing Power Parity) from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) and the growth therein. The key explanatory variable is the incidence of malaria (per 1,000 inhabitants at risk) from the WHO.² Summary statistics are provided in Table 1. Average malarial incidence in our largest sample of 3,104 country-years is equal to 68 per 1,000 inhabitants at risk, with a large standard deviation of 137. The mean level of GDP per capita in our sample is \$US 16,700 in 2015 PPP terms (standard deviation = 19,500), while the average annual growth rate of GDP per capita is equal to 3 percent, with a standard deviation of 6 percent. Whether in levels or in growth rates, and as anyone who has ever studied the determinants of economic growth can attest, there is an enormous amount of both between- and within-country variance to explain.

2.3 Our empirical specifications and identification strategy

Our aim is to isolate the impact of malaria on GDP per capita from other factors correlated with malaria that may also affect income. The recent tendency in the empirical growth literature is to focus on identifying the potential causal link and eschew including other covariates that may be correlated with unobservable factors not included in our estimation. As in GS, our specification of the GDP per capita regression in levels and growth rates (equations 1 and 2) can be written as:

$$y_{it} = x_{it}\alpha + m_{it}\beta + u_{it}, \quad (3)$$

where variables are now also indexed by time period t . One can then decompose the unobservables or the error term into a standard two-way fixed effects specification by posing:

$$u_{it} = \lambda_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (4)$$

where λ_i and μ_t are country- and time-specific unobservables, respectively, and ε_{it} represents idiosyncratic shocks that affect country-periods. We estimate equation (3) through multiple strategies. Apart from applying standard OLS on the pooled dataset of country-year observations, we also transform equation 3 into deviations with respect to country-specific means. This eliminates all factors that do not change over time for each country (λ_i) and bases estimation on changes in malarial intensity on GDP per capita *within* each country.

One concern that remains after purging country-specific effects is the existence of variables that do vary over time and are correlated with both malarial intensity and GDP per capita. This would mean that the malaria variable cannot be assumed to be exogenous (i.e. it may be correlated with ε_{it}). To address this we use an instrumental variables (IV) approach. A suitable instrument would be a variable correlated with malarial incidence but not correlated with GDP per capita through any other channel.

²The malaria incidence variable which enters in logarithmic form in GS, is transformed using the standard inverse hyperbolic sine transformation to reduce the effect of outliers and account for not being able to take the log of zero [4]: $IHS(y_i) = \log[y_i + (y_i^2 + 1)^{1/2}]$.

In this manner, any variation in GDP per capita explained by our instrument can be causally attributed to malaria.

We use three measures of IHME calculated drug resistance as our IVs; resistance to sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP), Chloroquine (CQ) and Artemisinin-Based Combination Therapies (ACT)[5]. Apart from such *external* IVs, we also use sufficiently lagged values of the explanatory variables as *internal* instruments. The Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) rests on the assumption that past differences and levels of the explanatory variables are uncorrelated with the contemporaneous levels and differences, respectively, of the error term (ε_{it}) [6, 7]. Of course, care must also be taken to avoid a proliferation of instruments or a weak instrument problem when using GMM [8]. Typical examples of running such growth regressions are given by Arcand, Berkes and Panizza [9].

3 Results

3.1 Level of income per capita

A large portion of empirical growth economics has been preoccupied with a “horse race” between potential determinants of growth - institutions, geography and international trade [10]. The literature has reached a tenuous consensus regarding the primacy of institutions over the other contenders. Table 2 makes a first, purely descriptive, step towards examining the relative importance of institutions and the burden of malaria in which we use data from a highly cited paper by Acemoglu, Johnson and Robinson [11]. The dependent variable (log of GDP per capita at PPP) is updated and is for the year 2000 as is the malaria incidence variable. While the original geographical covariates do not vary over time and are the same for the year 2000, the measure of economic institutions (protection against expropriation risk) used by [11] refers to an average over the 1985-95 period. Due to the slow moving nature of institutions, this should not appreciably affect the results.

Table 2 reports a negative and statistically significant association between the incidence of malaria and income per capita. Since income per capita and malaria incidence both enter in logarithmic form, the coefficient can be interpreted in elasticity terms: in a cross-section, and without any attempt at an identification strategy, a 10 percent decrease in malaria incidence is associated with an increase in GDP per capita of roughly 2.2 percent, basing ourselves on the results presented in column (5). Notice that while the elasticity of income per capita with respect to malaria incidence is slightly larger in column (4), which does not control for continent dummies, the negative and relatively large association between malaria incidence and income per capita is **not** being driven by the African sub-sample –whose income per capita is, *ceteris paribus*, 51 percent lower.

Estimation of GS specifications for GDP per capita in levels using our panel dataset are given in Table 3. When pooling all the data and ignoring country- and time-specific effects, our parameter estimates of the elasticity of income per capita with respect to malaria incidence are similar to those presented in Table 2. Introducing covariates and time-invariant country-specific effects and year effects in column (3), the elasticity falls to roughly -0.05. In quantitative terms, the results presented in column (3) indicate

Figure 1: The figure on the left shows the simple correlation between GDP per capita and malarial incidence. This relationship remains after both variables are purged of the effect of institutions, trade-GDP ratios, country and time effects (right).

that reducing malaria incidence by 20 percent is associated with an increase in GDP per capita of 1 percent, still quite a sizeable effect, especially when seen from the cost-benefit perspective. As with the cross-sectional results, restricting the sample to either the Commonwealth or non-African countries does not appreciably change the point estimate, indicating that the -0.05 elasticity is not being driven by the African sub-sample. Malaria eradication, corresponding to a 100 percent decrease in malaria incidence, would be associated with a 5 percent increase in GDP capita on average. This is still a very large number (refer to Figure 1 for a graphical illustration).

Table 4 attempts a more rigorous identification strategy so as to establish a causal relationship between the incidence of malaria and GDP per capita. Drug resistance is positively and statistically significantly related to the incidence of malaria (Panel B, column 1 and 2), a result also supported by the existing literature [12]. However, drug resistance is unlikely to have a direct impact on GDP per capita other than through its effect on malaria-related health issues. This two-stage estimation of the causal impact of malaria gives us a statistically significant and negative result (Panel A, column 1). The result is robust to including the lagged value of GDP per capita as an explanatory variable and using the Generalised Method of Moments as described above (column 3 and 4).

However, adding covariates related to institutions, education and trade renders the parameter estimate statistically insignificant (column 2 and 5). Two caveats need to be made with regard to this non-result. First, adding covariates which may themselves be endogenous (i.e. correlated with time-varying unobservable factors) may contaminate our estimate of the effect of malaria on GDP per capita. Second, Table 4 is estimated on a sub-sample of countries for whom resistance data are available - i.e. countries where

malaria is endemic. The reduction in sample size is compounded by the fact that adding the covariates increases the number of instruments significantly, thereby rendering the estimation unstable.³

3.2 Growth rate of income per capita

We approach the replication of GS's results for growth rates of per capita income in two ways. Growth rates of GDP per capita are often subject to extremely large yearly fluctuations. So as to smooth the data, Table 5 uses 5-year averages for all variables and finds a negative and statistically significant effect of the lagged incidence of malaria on the subsequent growth rate of GDP per capita. In contrast to GS, there is no effect of the log *change* in malaria incidence on economic growth that is statistically distinguishable from zero. Considering the results of column (2), a 10 percent drop in initial malaria incidence is associated with an increase in the yearly growth rate of GDP per capita of roughly one tenth of one percentage point. This number is estimated quite precisely with a small standard error relative to the size of the parameter estimate. Complete eradication is, for its part, associated with a one percentage point increase in the annual growth rate. Again, this result is not being driven by the African sub-sample: the point estimate remains essentially unchanged in the results reported in column (3).

Next, we again attempt to improve upon the identification strategy by implementing GMM using the system GMM estimator [7]. In Table 6 (columns 2-4) we use both lagged internal and external instruments to identify the causal relationship between malarial incidence and GDP per capita growth.⁴ We get a negative and statistically significant estimate of similar size to earlier of the effect of lagged incidence of malaria on subsequent GDP per capita growth rates. While the specifications pass the requisite statistical tests, the estimation becomes unstable once we add covariates. The caveats discussed with regard to the GDP per capita estimation in levels apply here as well.

4 Discussion

The recent empirical literature on health and economic development has shown that the link between the two is relatively tenuous [13, 14]. This is in part due to life expectancy at birth, the most commonly-used measure of health outcomes, being jointly determined with income and growth. Moreover, it is often the case that the disease burden, particularly in tropical areas, impacts economic outcomes via other channels such as the acquisition of human or physical capital, greater fertility, etc. [15]. Empirical work has so far failed to make a credible case for a causal effect.

In contrast to this literature, we have found that focusing on a single indicator of disease burden which is likely to be important for developing countries, malaria incidence, does point to there being an interesting link between disease burden and income. Our

³Ideally, the number of instruments should be fewer than the number of countries.

⁴Column 1 of Table 6 reports results of a growth regression that is closest in spirit to the original GS contribution: we consider the determinants of the average growth rate of GDP per capita between 2000 and 2015. There is no statistically discernible impact of either initial malaria incidence or the change in malaria incidence during the period.

preferred specification, which accounts for country-specific time-invariant unobservables and time-specific effects, indicates that malaria eradication would be associated with a 5% increase in per capita GDP, on average. A similar specification, but where the dependent variable is the growth rate of GDP per capita, indicates that malaria eradication would be associated with a 1% increase in the annual growth rate. These findings take the existing results of GS a step further in terms of data and technique.

More importantly, by using measures of drug resistance as an instrument for malarial incidence, we find a statistically significant and negative causal relationship. The estimates from an IV approach may, of course, not converge to the true parameter value but instead give a local impact driven by variations in the specific instrumental variable, also known as the LATE [16, 17]. This measure, though it does not correspond to the true impact of malaria on income per capita, is interesting in and of itself and warrants further study. Our claims in terms of causality are not robust to the inclusion of other potentially endogenous covariates and are subject to numerous *caveats*. However, they do seem to indicate that the association between health and income per capita and the various mechanisms through which this relationship plays out need to be revisited.

Figure 2 illustrates why this is the case in a particularly stark manner. Using the results reported in column (2) of Table 3, we first plot the actual 2015 world distribution of Log GDP per capita for malaria endemic countries, in red. In blue, we plot the predicted distribution were malaria to be eradicated. The upshot of Figure 2 is that malaria eradication could significantly shift the world distribution of income to the right, and that, unsurprisingly, the greatest beneficiaries would be the world's poorest countries.

Our findings are comparable to recent estimates from other empirical studies which use micro-level data to examine the link between malaria and development outcomes, relying on some exogenous variation to attribute causality. The discovery of the pesticide DDT and its use to interrupt malaria transmission is one such exogenous innovation in health technology. Bleakley [18] identifies the effect of childhood exposure to malaria eradication programs on subsequent adult labour productivity by comparing cohorts based on birth years before and after the eradication programs and across regions with high and low malaria prevalence. He finds that cohorts more exposed to malaria eradication efforts as children went on to earn higher incomes as adults. Persistent childhood infection of malaria reduces adult income by 50 percent and his estimates are similar for separate analyses for the United States, Mexico, Brazil and Colombia. A similar identification strategy applied to India finds that a 10-percentage point decrease in malaria incidence raises per capita expenditure by 1.5 to 6.8 percent [19]. In Uganda, findings suggest that malaria eradication would lead to 5 to 20 percent increase in income annually via improvements in educational attainment [20].

Our estimates, indicating a 5 percent increase in per-capita income from malaria eradication, are more conservative than the above studies. With 214 million cases of malaria estimated in 2015 (WHO), this translates to an increase of 0.15 percent of world GDP. Most of the above studies considered individual countries with high malaria burdens while we perform a cross-country analysis following Gallup and Sachs [2]. The gains from eradication would necessarily be greater where the disease is more prevalent such as in India, Uganda and the South American countries mentioned above. Secondly, our use of more recent data (2000-15) would take into account that the diminishing marginal

returns to eradication have already kicked in due to concerted international effort over the past. Likewise, projections of gains from malaria interventions would most likely tend downwards as found by the EPIC analysis however the gains would accrue mostly to the poorest countries where the burden is highest.

Figure 2: The world distribution of Log GDP per capita in PPP terms for malaria endemic countries: actual (in red), and as predicted were malaria to be eradicated (in blue). Simulation based on column (2) of Table 3 using enrollment rates instead of years of schooling for a larger sample.

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5 Tables

Table 1: Summary statistics - pooled

	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N
<i>Malaria variables</i>					
Endemic 2000	0.55	0.50	0.00	1.00	3104
Malaria Incidence (per 1000 at risk)	68.26	137.67	0.00	662.32	3104
Log Malaria Incidence	2.05	2.59	0.00	7.19	3104
Log annual change of incidence	-0.49	1.86	-6.42	6.50	2910
Mortality Rate	18.35	43.01	0.00	335.95	3104
Under 5 Mortality Rate	3.35	9.22	0.00	73.62	3104
Resistance SP	0.38	0.25	0.00	0.99	1484
Resistance CQ	0.81	0.19	0.01	1.00	1484
Resistance ACT	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.12	1484
<i>Other Diseases</i>					
Mortality Rate - HIV (per 10 ⁵ pop.)	46.45	117.30	0.00	994.24	2924
Mortality Rate- TB (per 10 ⁵ pop.)	17.68	24.57	0.00	165.21	2924
Under 5 Mortality Rate (All)	43.57	46.07	1.94	265.22	3104
Under 5 Mortality Rate (HIV)	1.60	4.97	0.00	50.55	3104
Under 5 Mortality Rate (Diarrhea)	4.24	6.49	0.00	45.24	3104
<i>Income variables</i>					
GDP per capita (in PPP 2015)	16699	19494	438	129207	2943
GDP growth (15 yr avg.)	0.03	0.02	-0.03	0.10	183
GDP growth (annual)	0.03	0.06	-0.98	0.83	2759
<i>Covariates</i>					
Rule of Law Index	-0.08	0.99	-2.61	2.10	2883
Avg. years of schooling	7.79	2.87	1.08	13.18	420
Colony	0.89	0.31	0.00	1.00	3040
Landlocked	0.19	0.39	0.00	1.00	3040
Life expectancy at birth	69	10	39	84	2943
School enrollment, secondary (net %)	69.64	25.05	3.19	100.00	1453

Table 2: Dependent Variable - Log of GDP per capita in PPP terms

	Base Sample (1)	All (2)	All (3)	Base Sample (4)	Base Sample (5)
AJR institutions	0.328*** (0.061)	0.273*** (0.055)	0.254*** (0.055)	0.332*** (0.059)	0.330*** (0.065)
Log Malaria Incidence	-0.234*** (0.036)	-0.324*** (0.036)	-0.283*** (0.042)	-0.278*** (0.038)	-0.219*** (0.038)
Latitude		-0.769 (0.477)	-0.628 (0.512)	-1.380* (0.614)	-1.241 (0.709)
Africa			-0.416* (0.197)		-0.511*** (0.146)
Asia			-0.041 (0.194)		-0.487* (0.236)
Other			0.008 (0.143)		0.157 (0.224)
Constant	7.325*** (0.496)	8.213*** (0.435)	8.329*** (0.421)	7.713*** (0.509)	7.745*** (0.508)
R-squared	0.734	0.746	0.751	0.746	0.776
Number of Obs	62	115	115	62	62

Note: $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$. All estimations are OLS with Huber-White robust standard errors. Data are for the year 2000 as described in text.

Table 3: Dependent Variable - Log of GDP per capita PPP

	All OLS (1)	All OLS (2)	All Within (3)	Commonwealth Within (4)	Non-Africa Within (5)
Log Malaria Incidence	-0.330*** (0.006)	-0.175*** (0.020)	-0.049*** (0.012)	-0.041* (0.018)	-0.056*** (0.013)
colony	-0.508*** (0.049)	-0.235** (0.078)			
Landlocked	-0.447*** (0.040)	-0.468*** (0.071)			
Rule of Law		0.435*** (0.040)	0.167** (0.051)	0.157** (0.056)	0.159* (0.062)
Trade - percent of GDP		0.002** (0.001)	-0.001*** (0.000)	0.000 (0.001)	-0.001* (0.001)
Years of Schooling		0.095*** (0.018)			
Constant	10.293*** (0.044)	8.940*** (0.183)	9.132*** (0.045)	8.783*** (0.077)	9.439*** (0.057)
Country Fixed Effects	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effects	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.566	0.789	0.594	0.595	0.612
Number of obs	2896	407	2609	730	1967
Number of groups			180	50	135

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Huber-White robust standard errors in parentheses for OLS and clustered at country level for within estimations.

Table 4: Dependent Variable - Log of GDP per capita PPP

Panel A:	2SLS	2SLS	System GMM (One-step)	System GMM (Two-step)	System GMM (One-step)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Log Malaria Incidence _t	-0.141*	0.024			
	(0.075)	(0.051)			
Log(Malaria Incidence) _{t-1}			-0.011*	-0.010*	0.009
			(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.008)
Log(GDP pc PPP) _{t-1}			0.971***	0.974***	0.979***
			(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.021)
Rule of Law		0.241***			0.015
		(0.073)			(0.027)
Trade - percent of GDP		0.000			-0.000
		(0.001)			(0.000)
Net Secondary Enroll.		0.005**			0.002**
		(0.002)			(0.001)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Panel B:					
<i>First Stage Dependent Variable - Log Malaria Incidence</i>					
Resistance SP	-0.980	2.565			
	(0.967)	(2.250)			
Resistance CQ	1.419*	2.821**			
	(0.785)	(1.155)			
Resistance ACT	8.569*	8.270			
	(4.630)	(8.143)			
Rule of Law		-0.245			
		(0.425)			
Net Secondary Enroll.		-0.000			
		(0.017)			
Trade - percent of GDP		0.004			
		(0.004)			
Number of obs.	1456	537	1456	1456	546
Number of countries	104	74	104	104	80
Number of IVs			45	45	89
F-statistic	9.34	5.06			
Hansen test of	0.0928	0.030			
Overid. p-value					
Kleibergen-Paap LM test of	0.037	0.052			
Weak id. p-value					
AR(1)			0.001	0.001	0.002
AR(2)			0.233	0.227	0.294
Hansen p-value			0.215	0.215	0.394

Note: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Huber-White robust standard errors in parentheses. Lags 10 to 15 of internal instruments are used for system GMM estimations in columns 3 and 4 and the collapsed set of lagged covariates in column 5. All GMM estimations account for the Windmeijer correction for small samples.

Table 5: Dependent Variable - Annual Growth of GDP per capita PPP using 5-year averages

	All Within (1)	All Within (2)	Non-Africa Within (3)
Log of Malaria Incidence $_{t-1}$	-0.010*** (0.003)	-0.009*** (0.003)	-0.010** (0.003)
Log Change in Malaria Incidence $_t$	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.003)
Log of GDP per capita PPP $_{t-1}$	-0.087*** (0.021)	-0.102*** (0.025)	-0.094*** (0.025)
Years of Schooling $_{t-1}$	0.005 (0.004)	0.000 (0.005)	-0.000 (0.006)
Life Expectancy at Birth $_{t-1}$	0.003 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	0.002 (0.003)
Trade (percent of GDP)	0.000** (0.000)	0.000** (0.000)	0.000* (0.000)
Rule of Law	0.043* (0.020)	0.044* (0.019)	0.048 (0.025)
Constant	0.597*** (0.160)	0.850*** (0.238)	0.736* (0.327)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.226	0.238	0.263
Number of Obs	275	275	213
Number of Countries	138	138	107
Number of Instruments			
Hansen p-value			

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Huber-White robust standard errors in parentheses. The dependent variable is the instantaneous annual growth rate of GDP per capita PPP: $g_y = \frac{1}{t}[\ln(Y_t) - \ln(Y_{t-1})]$.

Table 6: Dependent Variable - Growth of GDP per capita PPP - using yearly data

	2000-2015	Annual	Annual	Annual
	OLS	System GMM	System GMM	System GMM
	(1)	(One-step)	(Two-step)	(One-step)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Log Malaria Incidence _{<i>t</i>-15}	-0.001 (0.005)			
Log Malaria Incidence _{<i>t</i>-1}		-0.010* (0.005)	-0.011** (0.006)	0.010 (0.006)
Log Total Change in MI	-0.000 (0.006)			
Log Annual Change in MI		0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.001 (0.001)
Log(GDP pc PPP) _{<i>t</i>-15}	-0.016*** (0.003)			
Log(GDP pc PPP) _{<i>t</i>-1}		-0.028** (0.013)	-0.032* (0.017)	-0.025* (0.014)
Net Secondary Enrolment _{<i>t</i>-15}	0.000* (0.000)			
Net Secondary Enrolment _{<i>t</i>-1}				0.002** (0.001)
Life Expectancy at Birth _{<i>t</i>-15}	0.001** (0.000)			
Life Expectancy at Birth _{<i>t</i>-1}				0.000 (0.002)
Trade - percent of GDP	0.000 (0.000)			0.000 (0.000)
Rule of Law	-0.003 (0.002)			0.021 (0.025)
Landlocked	0.013** (0.006)			
Constant	0.094*** (0.027)	0.284** (0.127)	0.000 (.)	0.143 (0.136)
Country Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.363			
Number of obs.	81	1456	1456	540
Number of countries		104	104	78
Number of Instruments		59	59	120
AR(1)		0.001	0.001	0.002
AR(2)		0.222	0.255	0.360
Hansen p-value		0.090	0.090	1.000

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Huber-White robust standard errors in parentheses. Dependent variable is the instantaneous growth rate of GDP per capita PPP: $g_y = \frac{1}{t}[\ln(Y_t) - \ln(Y_0)]$ where $t = 15$ in Column 1 and $t = 1$ for all others.

Table 7: Dependent Variable - Log of GDP per capita PPP

	Within (1)	Within (2)	Within (3)	Within (4)	Within (5)
Log(Under 5 MR-Malaria)	-0.021 (0.029)		0.016 (0.036)	-0.002 (0.037)	0.006 (0.039)
Log(Malaria MR - all ages)		-0.031* (0.018)	-0.039 (0.024)	0.026 (0.032)	0.024 (0.037)
Log Malaria Incidence				-0.063*** (0.017)	-0.055*** (0.016)
Rule of Law					0.170*** (0.052)
Trade - percent of GDP					-0.001*** (0.000)
Constant	8.851*** (0.028)	8.869*** (0.030)	8.866*** (0.032)	8.957*** (0.036)	9.109*** (0.045)
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.523	0.533	0.534	0.556	0.597
Number of obs	2943	2891	2891	2891	2594
Number of countries	184	181	181	181	179

Note: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors are clustered at country level for within estimations.

Table 8: Dependent Variable - Log of GDP per capita PPP

	Within (1)	Within (2)	Within (3)	Within (4)	Within (5)
Log(Under 5 MR-Malaria)	0.026 (0.031)				
Log(Under 5 MR-HIV)	0.060* (0.033)				
Log(Under 5 MR-Diarrhea)	-0.254*** (0.045)				
Log(HIV MR)		0.089*** (0.023)	0.086*** (0.020)	0.069*** (0.022)	0.069*** (0.019)
Log(TB MR)		-0.061* (0.032)	-0.033 (0.027)	-0.057* (0.031)	-0.031 (0.026)
Log(Malaria MR)		-0.051** (0.020)	-0.046** (0.021)		
Rule of Law			0.154*** (0.051)		0.161*** (0.050)
Trade - percent of GDP			-0.002*** (0.000)		-0.001*** (0.000)
Log Malaria Incidence				-0.049*** (0.012)	-0.042*** (0.011)
Constant	9.200*** (0.065)	8.859*** (0.110)	8.965*** (0.095)	8.951*** (0.112)	9.036*** (0.096)
R-squared	0.579	0.563	0.603	0.574	0.612
Number of obs	2943	2891	2594	2891	2594
Number of countries	184	181	179	181	179
Country Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.579	0.563	0.575	0.612	
Number of obs	2943	2891	2891	2594	
Number of countries	184	181	181	179	

Note: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors are clustered at country level for within estimations.

Table 9:

Panel A: Log of GDP per capita PPP					
	Cross-section			Panel	5-yr avg
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Log Malaria Incidence	-0.378*** (0.044)	-0.310*** (0.061)	0.229 (0.324)		0.261 (0.240)
Log(Under 5 MR)				0.756 (0.987)	
Temperature	-0.000 (0.014)	0.043*** (0.010)	0.002 (0.015)	-0.000 (0.012)	0.024 (0.069)
Precipitation	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)
Rule of Law		0.501*** (0.078)			
Net Sec. Enrollment		0.012** (0.005)			
Trade - percent of GDP		0.000 (0.002)			
Constant	9.844*** (0.198)	8.222*** (0.503)			
Country Fixed Effects	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Panel B:					
	Malaria Incidence			Under-5 mortality	Malaria Incidence
MEI (wt)	0.217*** (0.016)	0.151*** (0.021)	0.035 (0.022)	0.010** (0.005)	0.173 (0.106)
Temperature	0.081*** (0.017)	0.012 (0.013)	0.011 (0.040)	0.007 (0.007)	-0.029 (0.189)
Precipitation	0.000 (0.000)	0.000* (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	0.000** (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)
Rule of Law		-0.199** (0.100)			
Net Sec. Enrollment		-0.036*** (0.008)			
Trade - percent of GDP		-0.004** (0.002)			
Number of Obs	2460	1114	2460	2460	492
Number of Countries			164	164	164
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	180.393	53.954	2.534	4.031	2.649

Note: $*p < 0.10$, $**p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.01$. Standard errors in parentheses clustered at the country level. Temperature and precipitation are both weighted by population. All first-stage variables are in logs.